

THE DOMESTIFICATION OF RAMADAN WORSHIPS DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN INDONESIA

MUHAMMAD FUAD ZAIN^{1*} and RIDWAN²

^{1,2} UIN Saizu Purwokerto, Indonesia.

Email: ¹ fuad.zain@uinsaizu.ac.id (Corresponding Author), ² ridwan@uinsaizu.ac.id

Abstract

This article reveals that the fight against COVID-19 cannot be done only through medical approaches, but also through religious approaches. The policies of social and physical distancing by the Indonesian government, which are aimed at stopping and reducing the COVID-19 transmission encounter obstacles of cultural and religious beliefs. Health reasoning versus religious reasoning. Government policies through circulars of the Ministry of Religious Affairs and the recommendations of the Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI) regarding the guidelines for performing Ramadhan worship during the COVID-19 pandemic is an effort to strengthen the social and physical distancing policies to be complied with by the public. The circulars and recommendations have shifted the practices of worship that has a public dimension to a domestic dimension. Those documents have also been a way to justify that social and physical distancing are in proper accordance with Islamic religious teachings.

Keywords: social distancing, Ramadhan Worships, COVID-19, state regulation, religion mitigation

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic is an outbreak with multi-dimensional and systemic impacts. It has been established by the WHO as a global pandemic. (Di Gennaro et al., 2020) There is no country or region on earth is free from COVID-19 transmission. (Panahi et al., 2020) Millions of people are infected and die globally due to this pandemic.

The Indonesian government, as stated by President Joko Widodo on March 2, 2020, has set COVID-19 as a national disaster. A report released by the COVID-19 Response Team of the Republic of Indonesia on April 30th stated that Indonesia ranked 36th in the world with a total of 10,118 people confirmed positive for the Coronavirus, 792 people died and 1522 patients recovered from the virus. The COVID-19 distribution map in Indonesia showed that the virus has already infected 34 Provinces and 310 Regencies/Cities.

One of the challenges faced by the Indonesian government in the fight against the spread of COVID-19 is the counter-productive attitude showed by some religious communities. Although the government has adopted a policy of staying at home and avoiding crowds of people, some religious communities still hold meetings that involve large crowds. One example is the Asia-wide meeting of Jamaah Tabligh in Gowa, South Sulawesi, which illustrates the difficulties faced by the government in dealing with the beliefs of some religious communities in Indonesia. (Muhtada, 2020)

The main command of the government's policies related to COVID-19 prevention efforts is the interaction limitation between community members. The policies demanding the people to apply social and physical distancing have changed the procedures of worship, especially for

Muslims in the holy month of Ramadhan such as performing daily prayers in congregation in mosques, Tarawih prayer in congregation in mosques, Friday prayer, and Eid al-Fitr prayer. The government's policy on guidelines for the implementation of Ramadan worships during the pandemic was issued by the Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia (MoRA) through a circular number 6 of 2020 concerning Guidelines for Ramadan and Eid Al-Fitr 1 Shawwal 1441 H amidst the COVID-19 outbreak. The Indonesian Minister of Religious Affairs, Fahrul Razi stated that the worship guidelines are prepared to help prevent the spread of COVID-19 and protect Muslims from being infected by the deadly virus.(Loasana, 2020)

These policies that restrict worship gave rise to people's resistance, some Muslim communities reject the policies because it was considered as an intervention on the right to one's religious privacy and an action that blunts one's faith in God. Statements like "Muslims should not be afraid of the Coronavirus, Muslim should fear Allah", "isn't Corona created by Allah?", "our fear of Corona will reduce our quality of faith to Allah " arise from religious groups that refuse social and physical distancing for the benefit of performing worship like normal days.

This article will specifically describe and analyze the government policies released through the circular of the Ministry of Religious Affairs (MoRA) number 6 of 2020 concerning Ramadan and Eid Al-Fitr 1 Syawwal 1441 H in the middle of the COVID-19 outbreak, also the Tausiah (recommendations) by the Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI) about the procedure for worship in the holy month of Ramadan during the corona pandemic (Covid-19). Therefore, the main data source of this research is the circular number 6 of 2020 of the Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, the Tausiah (recommendations) of the Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI), and several statements of the government and the elite of Indonesian Islamic religious organizations on mass media. The focus of this article is government policies related to changes in Ramadan worship procedures as a mechanism for mitigating the COVID-19 pandemic with religious approaches.

LITERATUR REVIEW

The role of religious teaching in explaining disasters to the community is very important so that the community gets proper literacy to understand the nature of disasters with full sincerity and acceptance. The efforts given to provide literacy about the Aceh Tsunami disaster with religious approaches were proven effective for trauma healing to the casualties of the disaster. Religious leaders have been using religious forums such as Friday prayers and religious study forums as media to provide explanations on the relationship between religion and disasters.(Adiyoso & Kanegae, 2013) Bimal Kanti Pail and MD Nadiruzzaman have conducted a research on the same topic, the importance of understanding disasters with religious approaches through the interpretation of religious texts to build community collective awareness about the nature of disasters.(Paul & Nadiruzzaman, 2013)

Other research positioning religion and religious leaders as important factors in dealing with disasters is done by Neil Ian Parker. According to him, religious beliefs have an important role in building the transformation of people's collective awareness to understand the nature of disasters and how to respond to them.(Parker, 2019) A similar topic of research was also done

by Danielle M. Hesse who revealed the importance of religion and religious communities in treating post-disaster traumatic children, through religious approaches, the community collective awareness of the nature of the disaster is complete and correct.(Hesse, 2012) In addition, Kyoo-Man Ha's research concludes the same thing that religious belief systems are able to be important factors in disaster mitigation.(Ha, 2015)

Dealing with disasters is not always all about health issues and the reconstruction of the damaged infrastructure caused by them, which normally are prepared by the government, building disaster awareness and literacy are also important and have been initiated by religious organizations. Like what was done by Muhammadiyah throughout Indonesia by establishing disaster management centers for disaster recovery and anticipation.(Baidhawiy, 2015) All religions explain the concepts of disaster and their definitions can be different from one another. Therefore, one of the efforts to overcome disasters is by presenting a profound interpretation of religious doctrine to encourage religious adherents to be able to understand disasters correctly and be able to carry out post-disaster recovery.(Gaillard & Texier, 2010) Interpretation of religious texts will influence the public's thought construction and perception of disasters.(Shadiqin & Rahman, 2018)

Another aspect that is also important in the context of disaster management is the cultural aspect of the community. The impact of a disaster is very complex and multidimensional, such as social, economic, religious, and psychological aspects. There is also a possibility of infrastructure damage if the disaster is a natural disaster. Cultural approaches are strategic to build clean lifestyles, nature-friendly attitudes, and disaster awareness.(Jogia et al., 2014) Cultural systems are an effective mechanism for managing risks arising from disasters.(Kulatunga, 2010) This article aims to analyze the policy of the Indonesian government in responding to the spread and transmission of COVID-19 by using interpretations of the teachings of Islam as a mechanism to build public awareness for social and physical distancing.

Social Distancing Versus Freedom of Worship

In inhibiting the widespread of COVID-19 and reducing the negative excesses caused by it, President Joko Widodo signed Presidential Decree No. 7 of 2020 concerning the Task Force for COVID-19 Fast Response as well as establishing the pandemic as a national emergency.(Saputra, 2020) Henceforth, all COVID-19 prevention programs have begun to be planned on a national scale. To strengthen the Task Force, on March 20, 2020, President Jokowi issued Presidential Decree No. 9 of 2020 which revised the Decree No. 7 of 2020. Backed by the new Presidential Decree, governors and regents throughout Indonesia have the authority to provide command and evaluate the implementation of the acceleration in handling COVID-19 cases in their respective areas.

Several policies of the Indonesian government in handling COVID-19 outbreaks include (1). Buying virus testing kits and drugs, and conducting COVID-19 mass rapid test, (2). Distributing masks and personal protective equipment, (3). Urging people to do social distancing and physical distancing, followed by a ban on crowding in large numbers both for

cultural activities and worship, (4) Urging people not to travel outside the region or abroad, (5). Instructing to work, worship, and learn from home, (6). Promoting to wash hands with soap regularly and spray disinfectant, (7). Appointing referral hospitals and laboratories for COVID-19 tests, (8) take a series of economic policies to maintain people's purchasing power. The Indonesian President also decided the period from February 29, 2020, to May 29, 2020, or 90 days as a national emergency to respond to COVID-19 disaster, and will be reviewed if there are changes in the situation.(Buana, 2020)

History records that handling disasters of disease outbreaks cannot be done solely through health approaches, it has to be handled in a comprehensive multi-approach, given the fact that the spreading pattern of the virus is caused by human relations. In other words, efforts to stop the spread of the virus must also involve cultural dimensions of the society such as healthy lifestyles and even faith that originates from religious teachings. Therefore, community traditions involving crowds, be that of cultural activities and religious activities, should not be conducted for a while as part of the social and physical distancing implementation.

The social and physical distancing policies formulated by the government have so far been considered unsuccessful, as proven by the trend of the increasing number of positive COVID-19 patients throughout Indonesia every day. The ineffectiveness of the policies is caused by the people's low level of compliance with them, and this fact proves further that the measures in combating the diseases are closely related to the culture and life outlook of the people that originate from the local wisdom and religious values. Although the COVID-19 threats make people worry about their health and safety, social relations in the spirit of gotong royong (mutual cooperation), sillaturrahmi tradition (socializing), and religious routines involving large crowd are however still stronger. So, there are obstacles to the implementation of social distancing and physical distancing policies in everyday life.

To strengthen the social and physical distancing campaign programs, the government involves religious leaders, traditional leaders, and local governments to take part in providing education and literacy on the danger of Coronavirus and how to deal with it according to WHO health protocol. There are three approaches to accelerate the success of social and physical distancing programs. First, the approach to local culture in the form of a campaign to overcome corona outbreaks by reviving local memory of outbreaks stored in folklores or folksongs so that people could easily understand the impact of the disease that will occur. In that sense, people will receive the messages by ease. Second, the religious approach by involving religious leaders who are members of the Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI) to provide education to the people who enter the realm of textual interpretation of religion as the basis of their faith. Third, is the approach of local government? The involvement of provincial, regency, district and village governments will take the national campaign closer to the people, local governments could take measures in their areas such as forming or activating health posts in the neighborhoods, which is the smallest unit of governance. These local actors will have a significant impact because their appeals are directed straight to the closest community, so that they have bigger possibility to be heard and then complied with.

The response of the Indonesian people toward government policies on social and physical distancing varies. There is a phenomenon of rejection, which in Psychology is called cognitive biases meaning the errors in processing and interpreting information. According to Masdar Helmy, the cultural and theological barriers to the policies are caused among other things by the widespread of perspective anachronism in the Indonesian society, which is an inappropriate perspective on responding to the spread of this virus. According to him, there are two examples of the most striking perspective anachronism.

First, socio-cultural anachronism, Indonesian society is characterized by a communitarian-communalistic culture, meaning that people in a social unit will socialize and take care of one another through a life pattern called gotong royong (mutual cooperation) as a form of social care and empathy. The sociological ties are often manifested through physical touches such as handshaking, hugging, and social gatherings. Stopping these communitarian manifestations, even for temporary, to prevent the spread of COVID-19, is certainly not an easy problem for the community, because they feel something is missing.

When people are forced to abandon these social habits, cognitive contradictions emerge between health reasoning, such as maintaining social distancing, and communitarian reasoning. This is why some Indonesians tend to ignore the COVID-19 preventive medical protocol as issued by the authoritative institutions. For some people, the medical protocol is interpreted as an effort to reduce the social meaning that has been firmly embedded in society.

Second, a perspective anachronism that was resulted from the religious understanding construction of a community that is contrary to the COVID-19 prevention protocol that circulates on social media. Among the popular religious narrations in the community are that death is God's prerogative, COVID-19 as 'adzab (punishment) of God for human sins, fear to God is above everything - including to COVID-19, and that social distancing is part of efforts to blunt Muslim's faith. This anachronism that is counterproductive to COVID-19 preventive medical protocols becomes a serious stumbling block amid the hard work of all parties in defusing and stopping the spread of the virus.

As long as it concerns the way of thinking and lifestyle of individuals that do not have a direct impact on public life, the above-mentioned anachronism should not be a problem. However, if it is contrary to health reason and public policy, then the government has the authority to take coercive measures to implement COVID-19 preventive medical protocols based on health and scientific reasoning. This is intended so that people do not hinder the state's effort in handling COVID-19. (Hilmy, 2020)

State Policies of Ramadan Worship

The spread of COVID-19 all over the globe this year caused changes in the religious ambiance of Muslims since the pandemic occupies the holy month of Ramadhan, a special month that has its own meaning compared to other months. The difference ambiance is a result of the physical distancing policy enforced by governments all around the world. Various worship accompanying the coming of Ramadhan must be adjusted to the policy.

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that it is a good idea for state authorities to consider not holding social gatherings including religious events to prevent COVID-19 transmission. "WHO recommends that any decision to limit, modify, postpone, cancel, or continue not to conduct mass gatherings should be based on standardized risk measurements. Virtual activities could alternate the events, they can be done by using various media such as television, radio, to digital devices including social media.(Dewi, 27 C.E.)

In the history of Indonesian society, the government's involvement in the regulation of Ramadan and Eid al-Fitr has been going on for a long time.(Millie et al., 2020) The government's roles in Ramadan are the determination of the beginning of Ramadhan, the end of Ramadhan, and the celebration of Eid al-Fitr. These decisions are taken through a determination session (isbat) conducted by the MoRA, MUI, and representatives of Islamic religious organizations in Indonesia.(Ahmad & Hassan, 2017)

For Indonesians, the festivities in the month of Ramadan are marked by several traditions, one of which is gathering and reuniting with family members. The practice of homecoming, locally known as 'mudik', is a significant part of the holy month, meeting family members in hometowns is essential to complete the festive celebration of Eid al-Fitri after a month-long of fasting. This year, however, the widespread of the new coronavirus disease has prevented people from reuniting with loved ones. With governments across the globe, including Indonesia, urging the public to maintain social distancing to stem the spread of the virus.

Nahdlatul Ulama (NU) and Muhammadiyah, the nation's largest Islamic organizations, have called on Indonesian Muslims to observe the fasting month of Ramadan at home to contain the spread of the COVID-19, which has shown no sign of abating. It is the largest and longest religious observance of the faith professed by more than 80 percent of the country's population and is a time for many communal activities, including tarawih (mass night prayers), bukber (iftar group meals) with families and colleagues, sahur (predawn meals) on the street, as well as family visits to the graves of relatives.(Atika, 2020) The government and Indonesian Ulama Council (MUI) have advised Muslims to worship at home.(Bhwana, 2020)

MUI fatwa commission chair, Hasanuddin A. F. said, with COVID-19 cases burgeoning and posing a life-threatening scenario, Muslims may not hold Friday prayers in the area until normalcy is restored and instead offer midday prayers at their respective places. People should maintain health and avoid scenarios of exposure to disease since it involves following the main goal of religion. Hasanuddin cautioned that people exposed to COVID-19 must self-isolate to prevent transmission. COVID-19 positive people can perform midday prayers at home since Friday prayers is a compulsory worship involving mass gathering that increases viral transmission.(Bhwana, 2020)

The secretary of MUI Fatwa Commission, Asrorun Niam Sholeh stated, there were several things related to worship in the month of Ramadan amid the COVID-19 pandemic that we must pay attention to. Among other things, worship from home and change the habit of direct charity into an indirect one. "The habit of almsgiving in the form of foods for fast breaking together, sometimes we invite neighbors or sometimes we attend an invitation, should now be replaced

by sending the foods to the houses of the needy." Likewise, the custom of giving zakat directly should be changed to giving it through trusted Amil institutions online, "If Muslims usually give zakat or alms to build mosque facilities and infrastructure, it is better for the donation to be allocated for handling COVID-19 first. Because today many people need help because of the pandemic."(Mashabi, 2020)

MUI and NU, the country's largest Islamic organizations, called Muslims not to pray together in the mosques. The government has not implemented a ban to close any mosques at this stage. "There is no splendor on the streets, the mosque is in silence, the new atmosphere we will feel, absorbing the true meaning of fasting that we run," President Joko Widodo said, encouraging Muslims to focus on private prayer and make fasting personal worship."Let's welcome the blessing of Ramadan as a moment to break the chain of transmission of the disaster for the sake of personal safety, relatives and the entire nation."(Masrur Jamaluddin, 2020)

MoRA appeals to Muslims to carry out all Ramadhan worships at home. The Director-General of Islamic Community Guidance (Dirjen Bimas Islam) of the Ministry, Kamaruddin Amin, requested that the tarawih prayer in congregation in mosques should be dismissed. "In the implementation of the fasting, fast breaking together should be disbanded, tarawih prayer should be performed at home, the celebration of Nuzulul Quran will also be erased, and Tadarus (reading Quran) in mosques should be canceled," He hopes this appeal can be obeyed so that the implementation of physical restrictions or physical distancing run well. According to Kamaruddin, the implementation of fasting and other worships conducted at home will not reduce the quality of worship in the month of Ramadhan. Carrying out worships at home is part of efforts to break the chain of the spread of COVID-19 in the community.(Maharani, 2020)

Governments in some provinces of Indonesia, including Jakarta, have enforced large-scale social restrictions to reduce the mobilization of people in their area. The central government has also issued a policy restricting inter-city and inter-province travel to prevent people from going to their hometowns and increasing the possibility of a surge in COVID-19 cases across the country.(Bhwana, 2020)

The policy was announced on Tuesday, April 21, 2020, after President Joko Widodo led a cabinet meeting and decided to ban the annual homecoming (mudik) in the festive season this year. The decision was made after the Ministry of Transportation's research showed that around 24 percent of Indonesians still wanted to travel to their hometowns. The issuance of the policy after the research data was released shows that the percentage had raised the government's concern, considering the capital city of Jakarta has become the epicenter of COVID-19 spread in the country, accounting for 50 percent of the nation's total positive cases.

Two of Indonesia's largest mass Muslim organizations, NU and Muhammadiyah, have advised people to cancel their desire for mudik in May, arguing it would exacerbate the spread of COVID-19 throughout the country. Muhammadiyah chairman, Haedar Nashir said that although mudik was an otherwise positive tradition under normal circumstances, returning to one's home region was simply not advisable during the pandemic. The organization hoped the

government would also issue a more stringent restriction to clear up any confusion among the public as to whether mudik was advisable during the pandemic.(Fachriansyah, 2020)

MUI issued six tausiyah (recommendations) Number: Kep.1065 / DP-MUI / IV / 2020 about the procedure for worship in the holy month of Ramadhan during the corona pandemic (COVID-19). The recommendations issued by the MUI are expected to prevent the spread of COVID-19 in Indonesia.

Here are six MUI recommendations regarding Ramadhan worships in the middle of the COVID-19 pandemic:

1. Inviting Muslims to make Ramadhan this year truly a momentum to increase faith, piety, sincerity, and draw closer to Allah. Also to do solemn dhikr, munajat, read Quran more, and pray to Allah 'Azza wa Jalla so that the COVID-19 pandemic and other diseases immediately be eliminated from the beloved country of Indonesia and other countries.
2. Inviting Muslims to comply with the health protocol so that it can break the transmission chain of COVID-19. If in an area is designated by a reliable authority as an area prone to the spread of COVID-19, then Muslims should not carry out worship that involves gatherings of people, such as Friday prayers, Rawatib (five-time prayer) in congregation, Tarawih prayer at mosque, Eid prayer at mosque or other public places, as well as public preaching or tabligh akbar. These worships can as well be held at everyone's home without reducing the solitude and sincerity of the worships. Meanwhile, tabligh akbar can be done online.
3. Urging Muslims to increase good deeds, one of them by helping the poor and needy (especially in their surrounding area), through the distribution of zakat, infaq, and Sadaqah. Zakat, particularly, can be paid sooner than the time (ta'jil az-zakat) without waiting for the night of Eid, while zakat mal if it reaches nishab can be paid faster without waiting the complete one year period (hawalaniil haul).
4. Calling Muslims to increase solidarity and help each other among humans, especially among neighbors in a region, both in terms of maintaining common health and mitigating the spread of COVID-19, maintaining order and security with each other, and bearing and helping each other's needs (at-takaful wat-ta'awun).
5. Appealing the government to restrict the annual homecoming to other regions. That is because the urban areas (big cities) in general are the epicenter of COVID-19 transmission so that if the community goes to their hometowns, they might bring the virus with them, and create another chain of COVID-19 transmission in their destination. Muslims are appealed not to go back to their hometowns, sillaturahmi (family visit) during Eid can be done online.
6. Encouraging mass media industry, especially TV and radio, to prepare various Ramadhan programs that are in line with the values of al-akhlaq al-karimah, the spirit of gotong royong (mutual cooperation), helping each other, and competing in goodness, to help

strengthen people's religiosity and togetherness in facing the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Meanwhile, the government through MoRA issued circular No. 6 of 2020 concerning the Guide to Worships of Ramadan and Eid Al-Fitr 1 Shawwal 1441 Hijri in the middle of COVID-19 outbreak. The circular, addressed to the heads of the provincial office of MoRA, the heads of the regional office of MoRA, and the heads of the Technical Implementation Unit (UPT) throughout Indonesia, was signed by the Minister Fachrul Razi. The guidance was stated to be following Islamic Sharia, it was prepared to prevent, reduce, and protect employees and all Muslim community from the risk of COVID-19.(Widayanti, 2020)

The guide to worships of Ramadhan and Eid Al-Fitr 1 Shawwal 1441 Hijri in the middle of COVID-19 Outbreak is as follows:

1. Muslims are required to perform fasting in Ramadhan properly based on the procedures of the fiqh of worship.
2. Sahur (predawn meal) and fast breaking are done by individuals or family, there is no need to hold Sahur on the road or ifthar jama'i (fast breaking together)
3. Tarawih prayers are performed individually or in congregation only with the nuclear family at home
4. Perform Quran recitations or tadarus at home, following the command of the Prophet Muhammad to illuminate the house with recitations of the Qur'an
5. Do not carry out fast breaking together (ifthar jamai') whether they are organized by the government, private institutions, mosques, or mushala.
6. Do not organize the commemoration of the Nuzulul Qur'an in the form of tabligh akbar (public preaching) by inviting well-known preacher and crowds in large numbers, both in government institutions, private institutions, mosques, and mushallas.
7. Do not perform iktikaf worship in mosques or mushallas in the last 10 (ten) nights of Ramadhan
8. Repealing the implementation of the Eid Al-Fitr Prayer which is usually carried out in congregation, both in the mosque or in the field. The fatwa issuance regarding to this issue by MUI is expected ahead of time.
9. It is urged not to carry out activities as follows:
 - a. Tarawih prayer from one mosque to another (Tarawih Keliling - Tarling)
 - b. Takbeer parade (Takbiran keliling). Takbeer is enough to be recited and echoed in mosques or mushallas by using loudspeakers
 - c. Short Pesantren Programs, except through electronic media.

10. Silaturahmi (visiting relatives/friends) or halal bihalal (forgiving each other), which is commonly carried out during Eid al-Fitr, can be done through social media and video calls/conferences.
11. Zakah management is urged to minimize physical contact as much as possible during the collection of zakah.
12. The distribution of Zakah Fitrah and/or ZIS (Zakah, Infaq, and Sahaqah) should minimize face to face and physical contacts as much as possible.
13. People in charge of zakah and/or ZIS distribution should be equipped with health-protective equipment such as masks, gloves, and disposable disinfectant wipes.
14. Performing Ramadan and Shawwal worships, everyone should encourage, create, and maintain the conduciveness of religious life by prioritizing ukhuwah islamiyah, ukhuwah wathaniyah, and ukhuwah basyariyah.
15. Always pay attention to the instructions of the Central and Local Government, regarding the prevention and handling of COVID-19.

Policy Matrix

Changes in the implementation of Ramadan Worship during COVID-19

No	Ramadhan Worship	Arrangement Policy	
		Normal Condition	During COVID-19
1	Tarawih prayers	In congregation in mosques/ mushallas	at home with the nuclear family
2	Fast breaking and predawn meal (Sahur)	Sometimes done together at state and private institutions	at home with the nuclear family
3	Reading Quran (tadarus)	Together in mosques or mushallas	at home with the nuclear family
4	Short Pesantren Program	Carried out in mosques, pesantren, or schools	Carried out online, or through teleconference
5	Commemoration of Nuzulul Quran	Together with large crown in mosques or mushallas	removed
6	I'tikaf on 10 last nights of Ramadhan	Together with large crown in mosques or mushallas	removed
7	Takbeer parade on the night of Eid al-Fitri	together strolling around the city/village	In mosques/mushallas by using the loudspeaker and complying with health protocol
8	Zakah collection and distribution	Collected with physical contact in crowd	Zakah is collected and distributed online. If zakah is collected and distributed manually, the people in charge must wear personal protective equipment like masks, gloves, and disinfectants.
9	Eid al-Fitri prayer	In congregation in mosques or yards	at home with the nuclear family
10	Halal bi Halal or Silaturahmi after Ramadhan	Together in mosques, offices, schools, and public spaces	Carried out online or through teleconference/video call

The basis of government policy through MoRA and MUI, as explained above, is based on two main arguments namely emergency and obedience to government decisions (Ulil Amri). The arguments for emergency stem from the statements of medical experts as well as world health institutions about the importance of social distancing and physical distancing to break the transmission chain of COVID-19. In the socio-political history of Indonesia, religious and state relations have always been in harmony and are two inseparable entities. (Muhammadiyah, 2015) Government's establishment on the condition as national emergency is in line with the

objectives of Islamic law (maqashid al-shariah), which is to safeguard five basic human needs, namely religion, life, property, reason, and descendants (El-Wereny, 2017) in the light of Saddu Dzariah legal principles (covering/avoiding dangers comes first).

The government with its political authority and power and MUI with its religious authority meet to construct the cognitive level of the people in order to build collective awareness about the importance of breaking the coronavirus chain. In the context of social science, the phenomenon of the unification of political and religious authorities as the efforts to build collective awareness in eradicating the spread of the coronavirus in Indonesia can be referred to as the perspective of Marx Weber's authority theory. Authority is one of the most complex principles of social organization in modern society, and the most important relationships between individuals or groups are based on some type of authority. (Njegovan et al., 2011) In building social and legal power, various authorities must be involved so that they become a force that can influence the collective consciousness of the people. (Finnis, 1985)

Jakarta Governor Anies Baswedan stated, "Ramadhan is traditionally including gatherings, such as fast breaking and tarawih, usually done at mosques. But this time it will be different, as those activities should be done at home," "Surely, this moment is an event as an opportunity to strengthen and increase piety in the family. Because everything is done together, the father leads tarawih, tadarus with father and mother. This is a very different atmosphere. Hopefully, this year's Ramadhan could increase worship activities at the family level properly." (Iskandar, 2020) The shift in the procedure of implementing Ramadhan worships at home during COVID-19 as a consequence of social and physical distancing is interpreted as an opportunity for the community to make the house as a center for education and worship as well as a place to work, to strengthen family relationships that are difficult to obtain due to the different monilities of the family members.

CONCLUSION

The efforts to reduce the spread and transmission of the coronavirus do not rely solely on medical approaches but many approaches, not only one party but multiparty. Indonesian government policy in reducing the surge of COVID-19 transmission in the forms of social and physical distancing encounters cultural constraints in the community. Among them are those based on cultural values and religious faith.

The government's policies through MoRA's circular and MUI's recommendations regarding Ramadhan worships during the COVID-19 pandemic is an effort to strengthen the social and physical distancing policies decided by them. MoRA's circular and MUI's recommendations have shifted some worship practices from the public dimension to the domestic dimension, the documents also have been used as a tool to justify social and physical distancing policies from religious perspectives. Religion is positioned as one of the instruments in disaster mitigation.

Reference:

- Adiyoso, W., & Kanegae, H. (2013). The Preliminary Study of the Role of Islamic Teaching in the Disaster Risk Reduction (A Qualitative Case Study of Banda Aceh, Indonesia). *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 17, 918–927. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proenv.2013.02.110>
- Ahmad, S. A., & Hassan, S. A. (2017). The Role and Effort by Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia in Consolidation and Determining the Beginning of the Holy Month of Ramadan and EID Celebrations in Indonesia. *International Journal of Academic Research and Business and Social Sciences*, 7(6), 968–978.
- Atika, S. (2020, April). COVID-19: Groups call on Muslims to pray at home. *The Jakarta Post*.
- Baidhawiy, Z. (2015). The role of faith-based organization in coping with disaster management and mitigation: Muhammadiyah's Experience. *Journal of Indonesian Islam*, 9(2), 167–194.
- Bhwana, P. G. (2020, May). Prayers at Home to Fight COVID-19 Spread. *Tempo.CO*.
- Bhwana, P. G. (2020). COVID-19 Impact on the Mudik Tradition in Indonesia. *Tempo.CO*.
- Buana, D. R. (2020). Analisis Perilaku Masyarakat Indonesia dalam Menghadapi Pandemi Virus Corona (Covid-19) dan Kiat Menjaga Kesejahteraan Jiwa. *SALAM: Jurnal Sosial Dan Budaya Syar-I*, 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.15408/sjsbs.v7i3.15082>
- Dewi, D. S. (27 C.E., April). Panduan Puasa dan Beribadah di Tengah Pandemi COVID-19 Menurut WHO. *Tirto.Id*.
- Di Gennaro, F., Pizzol, D., Marotta, C., Antunes, M., Racalbuto, V., Veronese, N., & Smith, L. (2020). Coronavirus diseases (COVID-19) current status and future perspectives: A narrative review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17082690>
- El-Wereny, M. (2017). The Objectives of Sharia between Tradition and Modernity—A Comparative Study. *Journal of Islamic Studies*, 5(1), 33–45.
- Fachriansyah, R. (2020, April). NU, Muhammadiyah advise public to skip 'mudik' in time of coronavirus. *The Jakarta Post*.
- Finnis, J. M. (1985). On Positivism and Legal Rational Authority. *Oxford J. Legal Stud.*, 5, 74.
- Gaillard, J.-C., & Texier, P. (2010). Religions, natural hazards, and disasters: An introduction.
- Ha, K.-M. (2015). The role of religious beliefs and institutions in disaster management: A case study. *Religions*, 6(4), 1314–1329.
- Hesse, D. (2012). Disaster preparedness and response among religious organizations. *University of Alabama Libraries*.
- Hilmy, M. (2020, April). Sikap Ilmiah Hadapi Pandemi. *Kompas*.
- Iskandar, R. A. (2020, April). COVID-19, Anies Calls on Muslims in Jakarta to Pray at Home During Ramadan. *Berita Jakarta*.
- Jogja, J., Kulatunga, U., Yates, G., & Wedawatta, G. (2014). Culture and the psychological impacts of natural disasters : Implications for disaster management and disaster mental health. *Built and Human Environment Review*, 7(1), 1–10.
- Kulatunga, U. (2010). Impact of culture towards disaster risk reduction. *International Journal of Strategic Property Management*, 14(4), 304–313. <https://doi.org/10.3846/ijspm.2010.23>

- Loasana, N. A. (2020). Ramadan in solitude: Religious ministry urges people to scrap joint iftar plans, mass Idul Fitri prayers. *The Jakarta Post*.
- Maharani, T. (2020, April). Kemenag: Shalat Tarawih Selama Ramadhan Digelar di Rumah. *Kompas*.
- Mashabi, S. (2020, April). Ini Arahan MUI Terkait Ibadah Ramadhan di Tengah Pandemi Covid-19. *Kompas*.
- Masrur Jamaluddin, S. S. and H. R. (2020, April). Indonesia has the world's biggest Muslim population. It just banned holiday travel over Ramadan. *CNN Indonesia*.
- Millie, J., Syarif, D., & Fakhruroji, M. (2020). Islamic preaching and state regulation in Indonesia. *CILIS Policy Papers*, 18, 1–40.
- Muhammadiyah, H. (2015). The Relation between Religion and State in Indonesia. *Asian Social Science*, 11(28), 98.
- Muhtada, D. (2020). Religion and COVID-19 mitigation. *The Jakarta Post*.
- Njegovan, B. R., Vukadinović, M., & Nešić, L. G. (2011). Characteristics and types of authority: The attitudes of young people. A case study. *Sociologia*, 43(6), 671–673.
- Panahi, L., Amiri, M., & Pouy, S. (2020). Risks of Novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) in Pregnancy: a Narrative Review. *Archives of Academic Emergency Medicine*, 8(1), e34.
- Parker, N. I. (2019). A narrative analysis of religious journalism's approach to disaster reporting.
- Paul, B. K., & Nadiruzzaman, M. D. (2013). Religious interpretations for the causes of the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami. *Asian Profile*, 41(1), 67–77.
- Saputra, A. (2020, April). Teken Keppres, Jokowi Tetapkan Corona Jadi Bencana Nasional. *Detik News*.
- Shadiqin, S. I., & Rahman, A. (2018). Islam and disaster: a refined concept through community's disaster perception of post the 2004 Indian ocean tsunami. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 6(3), 16–21.
- Widayanti, O. W. (2020, April). 15 Panduan Ibadah Selama Covid-19 Mewabah Menurut Kementerian Agama Indonesia. *Tribunnews.Com*.